

The Issues Of Tourism In The Integration Of The Town Of Bejaia In The Economic Development Process

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Abstract

The idea of this study on the integration of the city in the process of economic development is to determine other horizons of development through the tourist option. Nevertheless, Algeria has experienced a production of urban spaces structured in its entirety by the industrial function. The latter did not participate in the growth of the city. It has been a factor of the polarization of migratory movements towards the city without for that it generates a consequent urbanization consequent, in detriment of other sectors susceptible to an economic revival. Tourism can be an alternative to development, given the landscape diversity and the natural and cultural resources that the country possesses. But this sector has always been marginalized by land use plans and urban policies.

We chose Bejaia is given one of the coastal Algerian cities, located 230 km from the capital.

-Insert between the sea and the mountain; it overlooks a bay that resembles that of Rio de Janeiro in Brazil.

- Rich in natural and cultural assets; the sea, the famous Gouraya Park and the historical monuments dating back to Roman times.

-Characterized by its architectural and urban diversity.

-It has a port, an airport, and a very diversified transport network.

At the same time, it is lagging behind in its development, which is reflected in the deterioration in the quality of urban life and the lack of jobs, even though it has one of the largest industrial zones in eastern Algeria and one of the ports. of the most important in the country. This situation has aroused our curiosity to think about the concept of development, is it possible to support development in urban areas through the promotion of tourism?

The present work is the beginning of coherent answer to this problematic. It would then be necessary to identify directions for the future, that is to say, to trace the path of development by starting with the establishment of an economic platform based on the alternative of tourism.

Keywords : *issues; tourism; economic development; the city of Bejaia.*

1. Introduction:

The exceptional expansion of urban tourism since the 1990 has made cities, including their historic neighborhoods, important economic resources of national income. The urban quality of cities supported by actions of embellishment and amenities in tourist infrastructure (luxury hotels and major airports in Turkey, archaeological sites valued in Jordan), the uncertainty, however, remains in the field of security and political stability.

A condition that goes beyond urban reflections in the context of the tourist economy.

The number of tourists that receives annually the big cities, in particular Paris and New York is evaluated on average to 30 million each (Aouni Mehenna). For many developing countries, tourism is seen as a magnet for foreign exchange, helping to redress the imbalanced balance of payments and finance the rest of the economy. For some declining territories, it represents the only chance of getting out of the economic slump. "It is also a privileged instrument of territorial planning and a good way to fight against regional imbalances. (Kouri Djamel)

It is this question that raises a significant issue of study and affects the character of the city, its image, its places, and its various urban networks of communication.

The objective of this work is to highlight the tourist capacities of Bejaia the Algerian city, coastal, historical with panoramic landscapes, called to be essential assets for its development.

2.Bejaia, in its global context:

Fig. 1: Location of the city of Bejaia. Source: Author of the article.

Bejaia is located in the province of the same name, at a distance of 230 Km to the east of the capital Algiers, in a bay 7 km and inserted in a very diverse physical environment, between regions of mountains, plains and the sea, vulnerable to natural hazards, including floods and earthquakes. Bejaia is characterized by moderate Mediterranean climate.

Its population has grown rapidly because of the phenomenon of massive rural migration and natural growth, which increased from 101,657 inhabitants in 1977 to 177,988 inhabitants in 2008, according to the National Statistics Office. This demographic and urban growth has caused greater pressure on land use, including urban expansion took place from the old city with a high concentration of historical monuments to two growing areas, the plain of El khmis and coastline.

Indeed, urbanization was a huge jump from 500 hectares to 2285 hectares in just three decades (1980-2010), as the city has grown from 60 hectares in ten centuries of the period at the time Hammadid French (planning Department of the wilaya of Bejaia, 2007), urban boom has marginalized the old centre, especially with the departure of affluent layers replaced by a poor rural population and the invasion of various harmful economic activities in this fragile area.

3.Natural potentialities for the city:

Tourism has long been a very practical opportunity related to natural sites. The city of Bejaia has wooded urban spaces that give it a "green" city image. The woods of Sidi Ahmed, the olive trees, where the sacred wood are natural areas to classify. In addition Bejaia closes important natural wealth that we quote:

The Gouraya National Park: it is considered the lung of the city with its 2080 hectares; it has exceptional ecological and aesthetic wealth including flora, fauna, and historical and picturesque sites. It contains 198 fauna and flora species. Added to this is the importance of marine influence, the park being limited to the north by the Mediterranean on 10.6km. The park, due to its location on the immediate edge of the city of Bejaia, is an educational and attractive area for relaxation and recreation (see figure 2).

Fig 2 Gouraya National Park / Source: Gouraya National Park Information Center.

Functionally, there is a break between the park and the city, the lack of direct communication channels such as the cable car, which makes the site landlocked. Thus invaded by wild dumps and illicit habitat.

Fig 3 Cape Boic

Fig 4 Cape Carbon

Fig 5 View of the city from Gouraya

Oued Soummam: also considered as another abandoned natural entity that constitutes a disjunction in urban continuity, whose city must recover and enhance the two banks of the Soummam which are currently inaccessible. In developed countries, such natural elements are essential components of the urban landscape, like the Seine in France, which is considered a curiosity of the city.

Lake Mézaia: wetland located in downtown Bejaia. It is an artificial lake of 2.5 hectares with a depth of up to 18m in the center of the lake. It was originally a clay deposit, the development of a plant belt consisting mainly of reeds and rushes and the visit of some migratory birds has finally contributed to the creation of a new lacustrine ecosystem.

Fig 6-7 Lake Mezaia

The coastline: The coastline of Bejaia is composed of four beaches allowed for swimming, as mentioned in the table below.

Table 1. Beaches allowed for swimming.

Designation of the beach	Length (meters)
Les aiguades	200
Boulimat	1200
Tala-guilef	600
Saket	800

Source: Cadastral survey of the Bejaia coastline, CNERU

However, these beaches are left to their spells monopolized by individuals who take advantage of summer visitors and who undermine the image of seaside tourism.

In order to exploit its natural wealth for tourism and economic purposes, four zones of tourist exploitation (ZET) were created, but little exploited.

- **ZET Pointe des Moules:** Located 23 km from the capital. Its area is 52 hectares. The capacity of the building land is 07 hectares. The capacity of the land consumed is 4 hectares.

-**ZET Pointe Boulimat:** Located 18 km from the Bejaia, the capacity of building land is 10 hectares. The area consumed is 6 hectares. It is projected as a perspective to realize a large seaside resort.

ZET Adrar Imoula: Located 13 km from the capital on the west coast, the capacity of the building land is 15Ha. The area consumed is 1 hectare — the prospects of realization, a big seaside resort with daily seaside activities and important structures of reception.

ZET Gouraya: Located at 03km of the chief town, it contains the historic site Plateau Des Ruines. Its area is 134 hectares. The capacity of the building land is 21 hectares. The ZET is located inside the Gouraya National Park, thus the possibility of realization of a project of a cable car station connecting the city of Bejaia to the mausoleum of Gouraya.

Indeed, Bejaia has some natural potential, due to its privileged geographical location, its coast, its golf compared to that of Rio de Janeiro or Naples, these mountains covered with forests and dense vegetation.

Fig 8 Bejaia Golf

4.The heritage riches:

The rich heritage, cultural and historical populations, are more tourist destinations that are increasingly preferred (GMO 2000). Urban tourism is a factor of economic growth, whose tourism activities contribute to the diversification and even the growth of city functions. In return, the city must promote the development of tourism offer. This mutual benefit could be an opportunity and a factor for urban urban development and economic growth. Cities with strong tourist potential rely on the urban promotion of their old centers, valuing their historical heritage.

In this context, there are no precise data that differentiate tourist visits from existing heritage features in order to identify their specific importance. Cultural tourism in the region is still in an embryonic state by not receiving the necessary echo for its enhancement and thus its implementation tourist service, as we will see later. We, therefore, take into consideration the most endowed places in urban and natural elements that have marked the history of the site in the absence of the most frequented. This allows the identification of specific tourist polarities or spaces of the tourist offer in relation to history.

Bejaia is characterized in its western part by contact between the sea and the land in the form of creeks, but also by more pronounced contacts forming an uninterrupted series of capes and coves. The most important are Cape Carbon, Cape Bouac and Sidi Yahia Cove which ends the Gulf on the north side. Cape Carbon contains in its upper part a fort with Andalusian architecture housing on its dome the lighthouse. Beyond Cape Carbon up towards the west coast, stand the ruins plateau where we find historic caves and remnants of fortresses. The most important is probably those of the Aiguades, surrounded between the steep cliff Cape Bouak and Cape Carbon.

4.2. The situation of heritage elements:

Fig. 09: Location of historical monuments and valuable sites in the city of Bejaia.

The monuments are located in a disorganized, landlocked in the natural environment of the park Gouraya or within the urban fabric. The old fabric is superimposed on a ridge path of succession and talwegs one hand, and relatively flat from the other courses, located on the plains and at the entrance to the city from the sea.

The advanced state of degradation and abundant affecting these sites is due to the ineffectiveness of management by objective protection policy. Indeed, most of the monuments are overgrown, unlawful habitat or squatted by families and often inaccessible. This state has minimized its value urban, tourist, and cultural.

Considering the studies of the historical heritage of the city, a summary table has been prepared using the historical times, classification, and membership:

TABLE.2: THE MAIN HISTORICAL MONUMENTS OF THE CITY OF BEJAIA.

Sites	historic period	Ranking	home institutions
West rampart	Hammadids	Unclassified	Ministry of Culture
East rampart			
South rampart			
Bab El Bahr.	Hammadids	In 1900	Ministry of Culture
Bab el Bounoud	Hammadids	In 1968	Ministry of Culture
Gouraya door	Hammadids	Unclassified	Gouraya National Park
Casbah	Almohad	In 1930	Ministry of Culture
Fort Moussa	Hammadids	In 1930	Ministry of Culture
Fort Abdelkader	Hammadids	Unclassified	Department of Defense
Fort Gouraya	Spanish	Unclassified	Ministry of Culture
Fort Clauzel	In 1835	Unclassified	Forest estate
Fort Lemercier	In 1835	Unclassified	Forest estate
Bab El Marsa	Hammadids	Unclassified	Ministry of Culture
Bab Amsiouen	Ottoman Era	Unclassified	Ministry of Culture
Bab El Barr	Ottoman Era	Unclassified	Ministry of Culture

Source: information collected and organized by the author.

Fig10 Bab El-Bahr source: Author of the article, photos were taken on May 15, 2015.

Fig 11 Fort Gouraya Author of the article, photos taken May 15, 2015.

5. Accommodation and catering equipment:

Accommodation is necessary for the development of the tourist function. Bejaia has 29 hotels with a capacity of 1450 beds. It houses the tourist village of Saket, 03 seaside hotels. The table below shows all the existing hotels according to the statistics of the Directorate of Planning and Spatial Planning (DPAT) for the year 2010 and a field update in August 2016.

Indeed, of the 29 hotel establishments, 26 are urban hotels. This dominance of the urban type of hotel can be an asset to the promotion of urban tourism because the proximity to the circuits of walk remains a factor of the most determined in the success of such an approach of the tourism.

The spatial distribution of these hotels shows that the lower part of the French core is distinguished by the highest quantitative level in terms of accommodation supply. Despite this performance, there is the absence

of classified hotels, a deficiency that undermines the tourism function especially vis-à-vis foreign customers, as well as the traditional high-value historic districts of the upper part of the old center, represent the lowest level of hotels.

Between dispersion, concentration, and non-existence, the tourist function of Bejaia seems not to be linked to its site. Districts of greater cultural and historical value are deprived of hotel quality (classified hotels), or even without any accommodation structure, while the most important hotels are located in newly constructed areas, and in addition located in the margin of the animated districts. "Rebalancing and improving the quality of tourist reception in old neighborhoods are the actions that guarantee the operation of urban tourism on the history and culture of the area."

Concerning the restoration, Bejaia has some restaurants, as it is indicated on the table below:

Tableau 3: les grands restaurants dans la commune de Bejaia.

Restaurant name and location	Category	Capacity
Le Savory, 08 rue du vieillard	2*	40
Le Palmier, 02,rue Nacer Benyahia	2*	40
Le Mignon Brise de mer	2*	90
Le Diplomate 13,rue des Frères Kara	2*	50
La Corniche, Baie Sidi Yahia,	2*	80
Petit Bateau 10,rue El Houes,	2*	50
Le « A » 04,rue AEK Idjraoui,	2*	30
Le Seville 02,rue Salah Cheikh Amar	2*	30

Source: Monograph of the municipality of Bejaia 2015

In addition to the equipment mentioned above, the city has 13 tourism and travel agencies. In the light of what we have seen on accommodation and catering, we can say that Bejaia is very poor in this area, given its immensity and its invaluable tourism capabilities scattered throughout its territory. As well as, to bring the tourist, to feed him, to lodge him is not enough. The tourist moves for a specific purpose, to take advantage of the tourist resources and to practice some activities, it is therefore necessary to give him this possibility through the amusement equipment, in order to directly enjoy the tourist resources and ensure their exploitation, as he allows the animation from the resort or the accommodation center. As a result, the tourism sector recorded a rate equivalent to 4.83% of the national market. Also the lack of reception infrastructures and the modest qualities of their services can justify the very low rate in arrival and night of foreigners equivalent respectively to 3.63% and 1.85% of the national market (national economic census, 2011), thus weakening the polarity of Bejaia (Graph 06).

Fig 12: Evolution of the flow tour of the province of Bejaia between 2009 and 2013.

Source: Bejaia Tourism and Handicrafts Directorate, 2013.

6. Accessibility in Bejaia:

Bejaia has the advantage of having maritime access. However, its port of Bejaia is largely specialized in the movement of goods, including hydrocarbons exports, we will come back to this in the indication of the commercial centrality of Bejaia. The transport of travelers remains in an embryonic state, the passengers and goods of which share in turn the same embarkation platform. The redevelopment and expansion of this infrastructure by integrating a real train station for travelers, will at the same time a first step in the entry tourism. Because this accessibility is double for two forms of tourism, urban by the proximity of the port to the historical and seaside sites by a system of maritime circulation. The port serves only one destination, namely the port of Marseille, by a line opened since 1973.

Regarding the airport, the small size of its reception infrastructure, causing the sharing of spaces for embarkation and disembarkation operations between passengers and goods is a real obstacle to the emergence of an access hub. On the other hand, there are only two modes of passenger travel after disembarkation, public transport by bus, taxis and individual vehicle. Despite its proximity, the train remains marginal because of its rather discreet location.

The link of the airport with the modes of terrestrial transport (tramway, rail) will be a good opportunity to launch the dynamics of circulation.

Indeed, Bejaia is relatively well equipped with a variety of modes of service. But a balance is lacking between these different modes. An almost abandoned railway and a road network congested daily the absence of the tramway and cable car increasingly make local tourist wealth in a state of isolation.

Indeed, Bejaia is privileged by a double endowment. It is a city dating back to the Phoenician and Roman periods of which still remain some vestiges, flanked in the middle of a landscape shaped by the sea, the mountain, the plain and diversified fauna and flora. However, most of its tourism achievements are in a single area of activity, in this case seaside tourism. This is the only type of tourism that is of real importance, and the current form of development that provides a functional break between the city and the sea in terms of leisure excludes seaside activity in the city itself. In terms of urban tourism, the offer is currently underused. But also, its spatial and functional characteristics are to be defined.

Figur 13 Concentration of tourist equipments in Bejaia Source: Author + APC data October 2014.

7. The recommendations:

- Improve the competitive advantages of the coastline and protect ecosystems.
 - The industrial zone of Bejaia will be progressively relocated to recover the land.
 - The local-global balance, to develop the local economy it is necessary to aim at the world market to assure good conditions of stay and business to the foreigners, to the foreign capital, to the international institutions to attract and retain them.
- The development of the region must be structured by and for "service" in general, including tourism.
- Diversify and modernize the road network.
 - Develop public spaces and green spaces.
 - Create urban landmarks.
 - The development of the banks of the Soummam by two axes of circulation along the banks and a large recreational park, the project must take into account simultaneously the track of the railroad which passes nearby, the pipeline and the gas pipeline which are also not far from there and it must give an example to follow in terms of city-nature cohabitation in the strict respect of ecology and biodiversity.
 - The reconstitution of forests by reintroducing historical and creation species provides a large nursery with research laboratory, training center for the study of species to develop and the conditions for their preservation and development. They must be strictly conserved and protected because of the quality of their landscapes. This classification must prohibit any change of use or any type of land use likely to compromise the conservation, protection or creation of afforestation.
 - The association, the interaction of all actors and the harmonization between their different strategies, prove to be important conditions for the realization and the completion of development projects. In other words, territorial governance is essential for the match between economic objectives and social objectives. Here, territorial governance is understood to mean the harmonization of actions with a view to satisfying the interests of all stakeholders.
 - With the absence of a local development strategy, communities must think rationally and seriously about tourism as an alternative development and exploitation of local wealth, including the historic city, it is a space that will be dedicated to the tourist activity of artisanal production, the commerce of all kinds, leisure, rest. Either a succession of shops, small hotels, restaurants, terraces, squares, gardens well arranged in several walking routes, this will have the advantage of giving a destination and an address to the flood of visitors (like Djamaa El Fna in Marrakech).

-Adopt an urban planning generating specific land to service activities, by seeking ways and means to recover the different types of land (land to be recovered at the industrial area in the heart of the city) to achieve a city that aims to serve as an interface between Algeria and the world, through the development of its CBD (banks, hotels, headquarters of companies and institutions, consultancies and consulting ...). On the socio-urban level, the city is fragmenting and segmenting according to a mosaic of housing and equipment and bodes well for a certain crisis. It must be said that urbanism as a public action does not participate in the social and economic construction of the city. These spaces are real commercial turbines in developed countries, especially in times of crisis as long as the players in the institutional sphere agree to collaborate together and develop projects on the right scale, but to try to value and characterize the places in their intrinsic value, and also in their induced effects. Value, for example, public spaces, major transport infrastructure. Yet it is through urbanism that the urban economy is relaunched and that qualitative and innovative land supply is created, or the territories are made attractive, that the historic sites are requalified, that the we are revitalizing the spaces in crisis, etc. Thus it is recommended to restructure the mole Casbah and recover the location to build a ferry terminal. The Old Port will become a marina, marina and ferry terminal and in the long term these infrastructures will expand to occupy the entire promenade of the sea breeze after significant adjustments. (See figure n ° 14)

Fig. 14: Development of the mole of the Casbah and the old port. Source: PDAU intercommunal .

-Establish a geographic information system, allowing users to identify quickly the location of different tourist places.

-The tourism in Bejaia is confronted with the insufficiency of the structures of reception, the road network, the accesses, etc. To alleviate this situation, it is first necessary to encourage the development of Tourist Expansion Zones, which encounter several problems that are at their embryonic stage of development, by registering a delay in the development studies entrusted to them. National Agency for Tourism Development (ANDT), lack of basic infrastructure in certain areas (gas, telecommunication means, sewage disposal, ... etc.), Proliferation of illegal constructions, degradation of tourism resources (pollution, looting of sand, dangerous advance of the sea), and disputes over the land.

-The creation of beach facilities that ensures conviviality and good animation, such as health facilities: thalassotherapy center, fitness center and relaxation by offering therapeutic care.

-This is also to encourage training in tourism trades, which she has no training institution in tourism. Similarly, the university does not provide any training in this area. Individuals who want to work in this sector are formed outside the region, specifically at the level of the three major institutions available to Algeria for training in tourism, National School of Tourism in Algiers, National Institute of Hotel Technology in Tizi Ouzou and National Institute of Hospitality and Tourism in Bou-Saâda. In addition, lack of professionalism and economy (under unskilled pay labor), employers in tourism often do not want to use skilled labor. This observation does not mean that training for tourism jobs is not an indispensable element in the tourism development process. For future needs, in particular, it is essential to equip our study area

with tourism training institutions and to involve its university in this process. Such a project will create learning dynamic, by involving local professionals, and a dynamic of entrepreneurship in tourism (project leaders).

Finally, it is recommended to Promoting historical tourism, The World Conference on Sustainable Tourism in Lanzarote, Canary Islands Spain, 27-28 April 1995. At the end of the meeting, the participants appealed to the international community and called on governments, Decision-makers, tourism professionals, associations and public and private institutions whose activities are related to tourism, to adopt the principles and objectives of the declaration which contains 18 articles. For the most part, define the following approach:

Fig. 15: Tourist promotion in Bejaia

- Demonstrate the effectiveness of sustainable management, for the tourist enterprises, in the respect and protection of the historical heritage and its components.
- Minimize negative impacts on cultural heritage and maximize its benefits.
- The necessity and awareness of developing new tourist practices: alternative forms of tourism, in particular, sustainable tourism, in order to reduce the harmful effects of tourism on man and the environment.
- Develop alternative forms of tourism, seemingly more sustainable, nature tourism, local tourism ecotourism, agritourism, historical are all notions that are similar to this spirit. The objective is to create a space that is coherent with its environment and in parallel to create relationships of interdependence between the different elements of the city.

8. Conclusion :

The city of Bejaia is privileged by a double endowment. It is a city dating from the Phoenician periods, projected in the middle of a landscape shaped by the sea, the mountain, the plain and diverse fauna and flora. The presence of an exceptional historical heritage often gives the city a singularity, an image of identity and, above all, recognition of tourism even surpassing their local scale of influence, just as the existence of a particularly attractive natural setting is a sure value for the development of tourism activities. In fact, harmonious development of the latter is hampered by dysfunctions:

- Problems of accessibility, urban and economic functioning on the old fabric, particularly the lower part of the French colonial core by concentrating a wide range of equipment, and a periphery devoid of these structures.

- Lack of coordination between the actors responsible for development and socio-economic development policies. It remains sectoral in terms of vision and planning. All the actions have been subjected to a centralized decision-making system, resulting in ignorance of local situations and slowness in the application of planning options.

As a result, we tried to demonstrate the need for coherence for better exploitation of urban land, and the fight against urban sprawl, stimulated by the distribution of the residential function that allows the development of individual mobility. We have also found that tourism is an interesting alternative in the perspective of a social reconciliation with space, but also of openness and exchange in the context of the phenomenon of globalization. But the attractiveness of it depends on its interaction with the whole urban fabric; it is the relationship between the global and the local.

Indeed, the contribution of tourism to growth and socio-economic development is not the least; it is a source of income and also potential large areas of employment. To exploit these opportunities, economic powers such as the United States and France have not hesitated to invest heavily in the development of tourism activities. Developing countries have done the same and have attracted millions of tourists every year. Our neighbors, Morocco and Tunisia, have elevated tourism to the rank of one of their main sources of foreign exchange.

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